
BRIEF BIODATA

Dr. Ramasamy Rajesh Kumar

Honorary Faculty, Novel Global Community Education
Foundation, Hebersham, New South Wales,
Australia

Speaker, PAN India United Nations SDGs

Life Member - Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE),
New Delhi, India

Fellow – Society of Education, India

Fellow- Academy of Environment and Life Sciences, India

Dr. Ramasamy Rajesh Kumar, Post Doctor (China, Korea), Ph.D. Biotech, MPhil Biotech, MSc Biotech and BSc Microbiology (India), MBA HRM (India), PG Diploma Bioinformatics (India), currently pursuing MSc Counselling and Psychotherapy, PG Diploma in Data Science and Analytics and LLB (General) is a proactive Scientist, Biotechnologist, Mentor, Social worker, and Journal Editor. He worked in Worlds top QS ranking Universities namely Zhejiang University, Institute of Nuclear Agricultural Sciences, Key Laboratory of Nuclear Agricultural Sciences of the Ministry of Agriculture of PR China, Nankai University, Ministry of Education Key Laboratory of Pollution Processes and Environmental Criteria/Tianjin Key Laboratory of Environmental Remediation and Pollution Control, College of Environmental Science and Engineering, PR China, and Jeonbuk National University, South Korea. He was invited as a Visiting Scientist for the prestigious Fullbright Nehru Fellowship from world-known Prof. Dr. Brue E Rittmann of Biodesign Institute, Arizona State University, USA. Further, his work has been recognized and cited in the European Union Parliament policy "Carbon Farming, Making Agriculture Fit for 2030".

In his research and teaching career for 16 years, he has been an honorary Faculty in NGCEF, Australia, Assistant Professor at Lovely Professional University, Punjab, and Associate Professor at St Joseph University, Nagaland, India. He has also been a Faculty cum Scientist in IASER, Tanjore, Assistant Research Professor at Chonbuk National University, Korea, and Lecturer at Jamal Mohamad College, Trichy, India. He has also acted as a Senior Scientist in Lysine Biotech Pvt Ltd, Tanjore, India, Technical Assistant in the Centre for Applied Research and Development, Neyveli, India, and a Trainee in CADD (Computer-Aided Drug Designing) Division AstraZeneca Pharma India (P) Ltd., Research and Development, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. He has received research funds from various national and international funding agencies notably NSFC, China, CICT, Government of India, and was involved in LSRB-DRDO, and UGC, Govt of India-funded projects.

Apart from this, he has also acted as an organizer, Moderator, Coordinator, Course Coordinator, Convener, and Organizing Secretary, and hosted many national and international conferences and workshops. He has also edited and reviewed books and Journals. He presented his papers at various conferences around the globe. His works have been published in national and peer-reviewed SCI-indexed international journals. His research areas are Nuclear agricultural research, Natural products, Microbial Ecology, Bioremediation, Agro-Environmental biotechnology, and promoting UN SDGs.

He has inspired a lot of budding minds with his interactive talks and lectures on both online and offline platforms. He keeps himself updated by attending workshops and national/international seminars to back hands-on experience. For his continuous effort and hard work, he has been honored with World Teacher Award 2021 by the Educational and Psychological Research Centre India & UK, World Environment Day Hero 2019 by the United Nations (Environment), The prize of outstanding contribution 2016 at Nankai University, PR China and Young Scientist 2015 – Deccan Environmental Research Organization, Bijapur, Karnataka, India.

For supporting society he was involved in various social works including organizing relief camps, medical camps in rural areas, and support during the COVID pandemic through his Art of Giving Charitable Trust.

He is a member of various national and international agencies namely the Indian Society of Technical Education (ISTE) since 2006, New Delhi, Counsellor Council of India (CCI), National Academy of Psychology (NAOP), India, World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Connecticut, USA, International Society for Applied Life Sciences, Asia-Pacific Chemical, Biological & Environmental Engineering Society (APCBEEES), Hong Kong, Asian Federation of Biotechnology, Korea, European Federation of Biotechnology, Spain, Bioinformatics Organization, Inc., Hudson, Massachusetts, Board of Studies, PG Dept of Biotechnology, Bishop Heber College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli, TN, India (2009-10). He can be contacted through Email iamramrajesh@gmail.com
